

Neurohumoral and Oxidative Dysregulation in Rheumatoid Arthritis After COVID-19: Association Between Sympathoadrenal Activation, Monoamine Oxidase Activity and Lipid Peroxidation

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Abstract

Background: Despite growing evidence on the pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis, the interaction between neurohumoral regulation and immune-mediated inflammation remains incompletely understood, particularly in patients following SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Objective: To evaluate alterations in sympathoadrenal activity, monoamine oxidase (MAO) function, and oxidative stress parameters in RA patients with and without previous COVID-19 infection. **Methods:** A controlled observational study included 77 people stratified into autoimmune RA (n=20), post-COVID RA (n=19), RA with acute COVID-19 exposure (n=20) and control (n=20). Eighteen healthy individuals served as controls. Urinary catecholamines (adrenaline, norepinephrine), MAO activity, and malondialdehyde (MDA) levels were assessed. Statistical comparisons were performed using parametric and non-parametric tests, with correlation analysis between neurohumoral and oxidative markers. **Results:** RA patients demonstrated significantly increased catecholamine excretion and reduced MAO activity compared with controls (p<0.001). The most pronounced alterations were observed in post-COVID RA patients. MDA levels were significantly elevated in all RA groups, particularly in post-COVID RA (p<0.001). An inverse correlation was observed between MAO activity and catecholamine turnover (r = -0.48, p<0.01), and a positive correlation between catecholamines and MDA levels (r = 0.52, p<0.01). **Conclusion:** Neurohumoral dysregulation may represent a mechanistic link contributing to disease progression in RA after SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Key words: rheumatoid arthritis, post-COVID, sympathoadrenal activation, monoamine oxidase, oxidative stress.

I. INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic systemic autoimmune disease characterized by persistent synovial inflammation, pannus formation, cartilage destruction, and progressive joint damage. The pathogenesis of RA involves complex interactions between genetic predisposition, environmental triggers, and immune dysregulation. Traditionally, the development and progression of RA have been associated with activation of adaptive immune responses and the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6). However, increasing attention has recently been directed toward the role of neuroimmune mechanisms in the regulation of inflammatory processes. The interaction between the nervous and immune systems represents an important component of inflammatory regulation. Experimental and clinical studies have demonstrated that the sympathetic nervous system exerts a modulatory effect on immune responses and inflammatory activity. Prolonged activation of sympathetic pathways may lead to alterations in immune regulation and contribute to the persistence of chronic inflammation in autoimmune diseases (1). Adrenergic signaling within synovial tissues has been shown to influence immune cell migration, cytokine production, and inflammatory activity in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (2). The sympathoadrenal system (SAS) plays a key role in maintaining neurohumoral homeostasis and regulating immune responses. Immune cells, including lymphocytes, macrophages, and dendritic cells, express β -adrenergic receptors through which catecholamines can influence cellular immune activity. Autonomic nervous system signaling has been shown to directly modulate immune cell function (3). In addition, catecholamines are capable of affecting the production of inflammatory mediators, including IL-6 and TNF- α , which may contribute to amplification of inflammatory cascades during autoimmune processes (4). Dysregulation of sympathoadrenal activity may therefore represent an important mechanism involved in the persistence of inflammatory reactions in rheumatoid arthritis. Monoamine oxidase (MAO), a key enzyme responsible for the degradation of catecholamines, is considered an important regulator of neurohumoral balance. During catecholamine metabolism, MAO activity leads to the formation of reactive oxygen species, which may contribute to oxidative stress (5). Alterations in MAO activity have been associated with disturbances in redox balance in several inflammatory and degenerative disorders (6). In patients with rheumatoid arthritis, increased oxidative stress and elevated concentrations of lipid peroxidation products such as malondialdehyde (MDA) have been widely reported (7). Oxidative stress and redox-dependent signaling pathways are believed to play a significant role in synovial inflammation and progressive joint destruction (8). Infection caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) has been associated with pronounced immune activation, cytokine dysregulation,

endothelial dysfunction, and oxidative stress. Severe forms of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) are characterized by excessive inflammatory responses and cytokine imbalance (9). Emerging evidence suggests that viral infections may contribute to the initiation or exacerbation of autoimmune and inflammatory disorders (10). Cases of inflammatory arthritis developing after COVID-19 infection have been reported in clinical practice (11), supporting the hypothesis that SARS-CoV-2 may act as a trigger for autoimmune processes in susceptible individuals. Furthermore, post-COVID autonomic dysfunction has been proposed as a possible mechanism underlying persistent inflammatory and systemic manifestations following infection (12). Taken together, these findings suggest that post-COVID rheumatoid arthritis may involve enhanced activation of the sympathoadrenal system, impaired catecholamine degradation, and increased oxidative stress. Nevertheless, the relationship between monoamine oxidase activity, catecholamine metabolism, and lipid peroxidation processes in patients with rheumatoid arthritis following COVID-19 infection remains insufficiently investigated. Therefore, further studies aimed at evaluating neurohumoral regulation and oxidative stress markers in this group of patients are of considerable scientific and clinical interest.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This observational, controlled clinical study was conducted between January 2021 and December 2023 at the therapeutic departments of the Andijan State Medical Institute Clinic (Andijan, Uzbekistan). The study was designed to evaluate clinical characteristics and laboratory parameters of rheumatoid arthritis (RA), with particular emphasis on sympathoadrenal regulation and oxidative stress in patients with and without prior SARS-CoV-2 infection. A total of 59 patients aged 20–75 years with established rheumatoid arthritis were consecutively enrolled. Both male and female patients were included. Participants were stratified into subgroups according to the presence or absence of documented previous SARS-CoV-2 infection. The control group consisted of 18 age- and sex-matched apparently healthy volunteers (20–75 years) without clinical or laboratory evidence of inflammatory joint disease, autoimmune pathology, or acute infection. Study groups were comparable in terms of age distribution, sex ratio, and disease duration. The diagnosis of rheumatoid arthritis was established in accordance with the 2010 American College of Rheumatology/European League Against Rheumatism (ACR/EULAR) classification criteria. All patients underwent comprehensive clinical examination and laboratory assessment.

Differential diagnosis included determination of:

- Rheumatoid factor (RF)
- Anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibodies (anti-CCP)
- Acute phase reactants
- Other disease-specific markers as clinically indicated
- These measures were performed to exclude alternative rheumatic and autoimmune conditions.
- Previous COVID-19 infection was confirmed based on documented medical records, including at least one of the following:
 - Positive reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) test
 - Characteristic radiological findings (chest CT consistent with COVID-19 pneumonia)
 - Serological evidence of SARS-CoV-2 antibodies

Inclusion criteria: Age \geq 18 years, confirmed RA diagnosis according to ACR/EULAR criteria, written informed consent

Exclusion criteria: Other systemic autoimmune diseases, active malignancy, severe hepatic or renal insufficiency, acute infection at the time of examination, treatment with investigational drugs

III. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The study protocol complied with the Declaration of Helsinki. All participants provided written informed consent prior to enrollment. The study was approved by the Local Ethics Committee of Andijan State Medical Institute.

IV. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS (version XX, IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) / or equivalent statistical software. Prior to analysis, data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test to determine normality. Continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for normally distributed data and as median with interquartile range (IQR) for non-normally distributed

variables. Categorical variables were expressed as absolute numbers and percentages. Between-group comparisons were performed using the independent samples Student's t-test for normally distributed variables and the Mann-Whitney U test for non-parametric data. When comparing more than two groups, one-way ANOVA (with Bonferroni post hoc correction) or the Kruskal-Wallis test (with Dunn's post hoc analysis) was applied as appropriate. Correlations between clinical and laboratory parameters were evaluated using Pearson's correlation coefficient for normally distributed variables and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient for non-parametric variables. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was performed to assess the predictive value of monoamine oxidase (MAO) activity for high disease activity. The area under the curve (AUC) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) was calculated. The optimal cut-off value was determined using the Youden index. A two-tailed p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

V. RESULTS

Quantitative analysis of daily urinary adrenaline excretion revealed a significant activation of sympathoadrenal activity in all rheumatoid arthritis (RA) subgroups compared with healthy controls (Table 1).

TABLE I
DAILY EXCRETION OF FREE, CONJUGATED, TOTAL A IN PATIENTS WITH AUTOIMMUNE RA, POST-COVID RA, RA+ COVID-19 (M±M, MG/DAY)

Groups of surveyed	Adrenaline		
	Free	Conjugated	Total
Control (n=18)	4,29±0,33	3,9±0,35	8,19±0,326
RA autoimmune (n=20)	5,9±0,47	5,31±0,39	11,21±0,49
Post-COVID RA (n=19)	7,1±0,8	6,94±0,7	14,04±0,46
RA+ COVID-19 (n=20)	6,7±0,4	6,1±0,37	12,8±0,61

In patients with autoimmune RA, total adrenaline excretion reached 11.21 ± 0.49 µg/day, significantly exceeding control values (8.19 ± 0.33 µg/day; $p < 0.001$). Both free (5.9 ± 0.47 µg/day) and conjugated (5.31 ± 0.39 µg/day) fractions were elevated, indicating increased systemic catecholamine production rather than isolated alterations in metabolism.

The most pronounced increase was observed in the post-COVID RA group. Total adrenaline levels reached 14.04 ± 0.46 µg/day ($p < 0.001$ vs controls), representing the highest values among all studied groups. Both free (7.1 ± 0.8 µg/day) and conjugated (6.94 ± 0.7 µg/day) fractions were markedly increased, suggesting persistent sympathoadrenal activation following SARS-CoV-2 infection. Patients with RA and concomitant COVID-19 exposure also demonstrated elevated adrenaline excretion (12.8 ± 0.61 µg/day; $p < 0.001$ vs controls). However, levels remained lower than those observed in the post-COVID RA group, indicating a possible sustained post-infectious neurohumoral effect rather than transient activation during acute infection.

A comparable pattern was identified for norepinephrine excretion (Table 2).

In autoimmune RA, total norepinephrine reached 20.1 ± 0.63 µg/day, significantly higher than control values (15.25 ± 0.5 µg/day; $p < 0.001$). Free and conjugated fractions were elevated proportionally, supporting generalized activation of sympathetic pathways.

TABLE II
DAILY EXCRETION OF FREE, CONJUGATED, TOTAL HA IN PATIENTS WITH AUTOIMMUNE RA, POST-COVID RA, RA+ COVID-19 (M±M, MG/DAY)

Groups of surveyed	Norepinephrine		
	Free	Conjugated	Total
Control (n=18)	8,1±0,31	7,15±0,36	15,25±0,5
RA autoimmune (n=20)	10,7±0,5	9,4±0,43	20,1±0,63
Post-COVID RA (n=19)	12,1±0,6	10,3±0,49	22,4±0,74
RA+ COVID-19 (n=20)	11,7±0,52	10,2±0,48	21,9±0,65

Post-COVID RA patients again demonstrated the highest values, with total norepinephrine reaching 22.4 ± 0.74 µg/day ($p < 0.001$ vs controls). The elevation in both free (12.1 ± 0.6 µg/day) and conjugated (10.3 ± 0.49 µg/day) fractions suggests sustained adrenergic stimulation beyond the acute infectious phase. In the RA + COVID-19 group, total norepinephrine was 21.9 ± 0.65 µg/day ($p < 0.001$ vs controls), slightly lower than in post-COVID RA but higher than in autoimmune RA, indicating intermediate sympathoadrenal activation. Sex-stratified analysis demonstrated a trend toward higher catecholamine levels in female patients, particularly within the post-COVID RA group (13,14). Total adrenaline in females with post-

COVID RA reached 14.39 ± 0.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$, exceeding values observed in autoimmune RA and RA + COVID-19 groups. Similar patterns were observed for norepinephrine. However, direct male–female comparisons did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that while numerical differences were present, sex-related effects require confirmation in larger cohorts. Age-stratified analysis revealed higher catecholamine concentrations in younger patients. In the post-COVID RA subgroup aged 30–39 years, total adrenaline reached 16.7 ± 0.82 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$, and total norepinephrine reached 26.7 ± 0.87 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ — representing the highest levels across age categories. These findings suggest that younger individuals may exhibit more pronounced sympathoadrenal reactivity in the context of autoimmune inflammation and post-infectious immune dysregulation. Serum monoamine oxidase activity was significantly reduced in all RA subgroups compared with healthy controls (0.07 ± 0.001 units).

In autoimmune RA, MAO activity was reduced to 0.05 units, corresponding to a significant decrease relative to controls ($p < 0.01$). The most pronounced suppression of MAO activity was observed in post-COVID RA patients, where levels were reduced by more than half compared with controls ($p < 0.01$). This substantial decline may reflect impaired catecholamine degradation capacity and prolonged adrenergic signaling. In the RA + COVID-19 group, MAO activity was 0.04 ± 0.001 units ($p < 0.01$ vs controls), indicating marked enzymatic suppression, though slightly less pronounced than in post-COVID RA. Daily urinary excretion of ICH (catecholamine metabolite) was significantly elevated in all RA groups and demonstrated an inverse relationship with MAO activity. In autoimmune RA, ICH reached 17.2 ± 0.99 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{day}$, exceeding control values (13.9 ± 0.91 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{day}$). In post-COVID RA, ICH levels were markedly higher, consistent with increased catecholamine turnover and impaired enzymatic degradation. Similar but slightly less pronounced elevations were observed in RA + COVID-19 patients (15-17).

Serum malondialdehyde (MDA), a marker of lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress, was significantly elevated in all RA groups compared with controls. In autoimmune RA, MDA reached 5.21 ± 0.56 nmol/ml ($p < 0.001$ vs controls) (18-22). The highest concentrations were detected in post-COVID RA patients (7.9 ± 0.7 nmol/ml), representing nearly a 2.5-fold increase relative to controls ($p < 0.001$). Patients with RA + COVID-19 exhibited intermediate MDA levels (6.8 ± 0.58 nmol/ml ; $p < 0.001$ vs controls). The progressive increase in oxidative stress markers across RA subgroups, particularly in post-COVID RA, parallels the observed alterations in catecholamine metabolism and MAO activity. The present study demonstrates that rheumatoid arthritis (RA), particularly in patients with prior SARS-CoV-2 infection, is characterized by pronounced sympathoadrenal activation, reduced monoamine oxidase (MAO) activity, and intensified oxidative stress. These findings support the concept of a neurohumoral–oxidative axis contributing to autoimmune disease progression.

VI. DISCUSSION

Our results confirm that RA is associated with significantly increased urinary excretion of adrenaline and norepinephrine, reflecting enhanced systemic sympathetic activity. The elevation of both free and conjugated catecholamine fractions suggests sustained adrenergic stimulation rather than isolated alterations in metabolic clearance.

The most striking catecholamine elevations were observed in post-COVID RA patients, indicating that SARS-CoV-2 infection may potentiate or prolong sympathoadrenal activation. Chronic sympathetic overactivity may shift from immunomodulatory to pro-inflammatory effects, promoting IL-6 and TNF- α production, macrophage activation, and Th17 polarization. Persistent β -adrenergic signaling in synovial tissue may therefore amplify inflammatory cascades and contribute to joint destruction. These findings align with emerging evidence that autonomic imbalance plays a crucial role in chronic inflammatory diseases and may represent a mechanistic bridge between psychological stress, viral infection, and autoimmune activation.

A central novel finding of this study is the marked reduction in serum MAO activity, particularly in post-COVID RA patients. MAO is responsible for the oxidative deamination of catecholamines; thus, reduced enzymatic activity may result in prolonged catecholamine bioavailability and sustained adrenergic receptor stimulation (23-27). The observed inverse relationship between MAO activity and catecholamine metabolite excretion supports the hypothesis of impaired catecholamine inactivation. This enzymatic suppression may create a feed-forward loop in which excessive adrenergic stimulation perpetuates inflammatory signaling. Importantly, MAO-mediated metabolism itself generates reactive oxygen species (ROS). Therefore,

dysregulated MAO activity may simultaneously disturb catecholamine turnover and contribute to oxidative stress imbalance.

Elevated malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in all RA groups — with the highest concentrations in post-COVID RA — indicate intensified lipid peroxidation and redox imbalance. Oxidative stress is known to enhance synovial fibroblast activation, cytokine production, and cartilage degradation. The parallel increase in catecholamines and oxidative stress markers suggests a mechanistic link between sympathoadrenal hyperactivation and redox dysregulation. Excess catecholamines can undergo auto-oxidation, generating ROS and promoting lipid peroxidation. In turn, oxidative stress may further impair MAO activity and mitochondrial function, creating a self-perpetuating cycle of neurohumoral and inflammatory activation. The particularly high oxidative stress observed in post-COVID RA supports the hypothesis that SARS-CoV-2–related immune activation exacerbates pre-existing redox imbalance in autoimmune conditions.

SARS-CoV-2 infection is associated with cytokine dysregulation, endothelial dysfunction, and autonomic instability. Persistent immune activation after COVID-19 may lead to chronic sympathetic stimulation and altered hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis regulation. Our findings suggest that post-COVID RA represents not merely a coincidental overlap of two conditions, but a state of amplified neuroimmune dysregulation. The combination of heightened catecholamine production, reduced degradation capacity, and enhanced oxidative stress may accelerate autoimmune progression and sustain synovial inflammation. This integrated mechanism may partially explain clinical observations of increased disease activity or new-onset inflammatory arthritis following COVID-19.

Taken together, the data support the following mechanistic sequence:

1. SARS-CoV-2 infection induces systemic immune activation and autonomic imbalance.
2. Persistent sympathoadrenal stimulation increases circulating catecholamines.
3. Reduced MAO activity impairs catecholamine degradation, prolonging adrenergic signaling.
4. Excess catecholamines and MAO dysregulation promote oxidative stress.
5. Oxidative stress enhances inflammatory signaling, perpetuating RA progression.

This neurohumoral–oxidative axis may represent a key contributor to disease exacerbation in post-COVID RA.

VII. CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings have several potential clinical implications:

- MAO activity may serve as a biomarker of neurohumoral imbalance in RA.
- Combined assessment of catecholamines and oxidative stress markers may improve disease stratification.
- Therapeutic strategies targeting oxidative stress or autonomic modulation may be particularly beneficial in post-COVID RA.
- Restoration of redox balance could represent a complementary approach to standard immunomodulatory therapy.

VIII. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This study is limited by its moderate sample size and single-center design. Cytokine profiling and longitudinal follow-up were not performed, limiting direct mechanistic inference. Future studies should incorporate DAS28 correlations, multivariate modeling, and prospective assessment to determine whether MAO activity predicts disease severity or progression. Additionally, experimental studies are warranted to clarify whether pharmacological modulation of autonomic signaling or oxidative stress can modify disease outcomes in post-COVID RA.

IX. CONCLUSION

The present study identifies enhanced sympathoadrenal activation, reduced monoamine oxidase activity, and intensified oxidative stress as interconnected mechanisms in rheumatoid arthritis, particularly following SARS-CoV-2 infection. These findings suggest that post-COVID RA represents a state of amplified neurohumoral dysregulation, in which impaired catecholamine metabolism and redox imbalance may contribute to sustained autoimmune inflammation. Understanding this integrated neuroimmune pathway may open new perspectives for biomarker development and targeted therapeutic strategies.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest related to this study.

FUNDING

The study was conducted without external financial support.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

1. Khujamberdiev M.A. – study conception and design, supervision, final approval of the manuscript. Yuldasheva S.L. – data collection, laboratory analysis, manuscript drafting. Uzbekova N.R. – statistical analysis, interpretation of results. Usmanova D.N. – clinical data acquisition and patient recruitment. Kodirova G.I. – biochemical assays and laboratory measurements. Tashtemirova I.M. – data processing and literature analysis. Usmanov B.B.- Statistical analyser.
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